

World News of Natural Sciences

An International Scientific Journal

WNOFNS 66 (2026) 101-124

EISSN 2543-5426

Appraising the effects of storage periods on the quality of sachet and pet-bottled waters consumed within a Nigerian University Campus

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ABSTRACT

Consumption of clean potable water is essential to public human health. This study was piloted to appraise the effects of prolonged storage periods at normal room temperature on the physico-chemical quality of two popular brands of packaged water (sachet and bottled) consumed by staff and students of Federal University in Southwest, Nigeria. Sachet and bottled water samples were collected within 24 hours of production and stored for different periods. Thirty two samples of water brands (pet-bottled and sachet) were collected and analyzed using standard physico-chemical methods to determine the concentrations and behavior of various water quality parameters over the storage periods. The outcomes obtained revealed that most of the physico-chemical variables were within the allowable limits set by the World Health Organization and Standard Organization of Nigeria for drinking water throughout the storage durations. Higher values of biochemical oxygen demand and chemical oxygen demand (above threshold limits) were conspicuously recorded for 2 weeks, 1-month, 2- month and 3-month storage samples, which indicated no effective quality control scheme. However, computed water quality index values for prolonged stored samples denote satisfactory status for drinking purpose. Relevant regulatory agencies should ensure that packaged water factories unceasingly complied with standard water treatment processes for improved public health in the study location.

Keywords: Packaged water, prolonged storage durations, sachet and pet-bottled, physico-chemical properties, room temperature, water quality index

1. INTRODUCTION

Human beings need safe and clean water for drinking purpose as this promotes good health and prevent incidence of water-borne diseases (El Hammioui *et al.*, 2022; Okeola *et al.*, 2023, Balogun *et al.*, 2024). In fact, providing easy access to potable water for populace is a vital component of their basic right (Boadi *et al.*, 2023; Ekanem *et al.*, 2025). Availability of packaged water plays a decisive role towards achieving United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 6.1, which is universal access to safe and affordable drinking water (Ekanem *et al.*, 2025).

According to Global reports, current percentages of people lacking access to potable water supply due to urbanization, climate change, and inadequate provision of pipe-borne water supply by the government (Ganiyu *et al.*, 2022a; Mergia *et al.*, 2025). Approximately 412 million people on the continent were without potable water as at the end of the year 2020 (Boadi *et al.*, 2023; Olalekan *et al.*, 2023). In local context, about 70 million Nigerians lack access to clean and potable water (World Bank Report, 2021; Adesakin *et al.*, 2022).

Since safe and clean water promote good well-being, there must be universal access to potable drinking water. There comes a packaged water that readily bridges the potable water gap via its feature of affordability, availability, accessibility and relatively of low cost (Boadi *et al.*, 2023; Hammond *et al.*, 2024).

Sachet water is a treated drinking water that is mechanically sealed in a 250 – 500 mL poly-ethylene poach while bottled water is a kind of treated water corked in 500 – 750 mL poly-ethylene terephthalate container (Sabo *et al.*, 2024; Ekanem *et al.*, 2025). Of the two types of packaged water, the consumption of sachet water is relatively higher than that of bottled water in most peri-urban and urban settings in Africa, including Nigeria. The general perception among populace of West African countries, including Nigeria is that packaged water is safer, cleaner and fit for drinking than well/borehole and piped water because it has undergone proper treatment processes (Akintelu *et al.*, 2021; Mulualem *et al.*, 2023).

However, there are some challenges and concerns about the safety and quality status of packaged water. Published studies have documented inconsistent quality, non-adherence to regulatory guidelines, inadequate treatment processes, and non-registration of brands with the statutory regulatory authorities for packaged water (Tenebe *et al.*, 2023; Douгна *et al.*, 2024). In addition, most distributors of packaged waters buy in large quantities and transport them inside open trucks, allowing direct exposure to sunlight. Furthermore, some retailers and vendors store bags of packaged water in open cages for several weeks before selling them (Adesakin *et al.*, 2022; Tenebe *et al.*, 2023). Thus, a risk of recontamination exists during the transportation, distribution, retailing and consumers' storage of packaged water (Tenebe *et al.*, 2023; Hammnod *et al.*, 2024).

There are several published studies detailing the impacts of long storage time and storage conditions on the physico-chemical and microbial content of packaged water (Okeola *et al.*, 2023; Sabo *et al.*, 2024; Douгна *et al.*, 2024); on phthalates/microplastics (Zuccarello *et al.*, 2019; Razali *et al.*, 2021; Ravanbakhsh *et al.*, 2022). Despite the laudable outcomes of these studies, the storage time for the packaged water samples ranged from 2 weeks to 4 months after the production stage. To the best of the authors knowledge, there is limited research or published evaluation considering the impacts of prolonged storage period (beyond 4 months) on the concentrations of physico-chemical parameters in packaged water (sachet and pet-bottled) sold and consumed within peri-urban and urban settings, as well as on university

campus. Furthermore, parameters like biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), chemical oxygen demand (COD) and oxidation reduction potential (ORP) were mostly excluded from the physico-chemical analysis of the packaged water. Thus, this research intends to fill the identified research gap concerning the impact of prolonged storage time (a week, 2-week, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6 months) under room temperature on the concentrations of major anions, cations, dissolved oxygen, BOD, COD and ORP in packaged water consumed within university campus.

Considering the high demand for and consumption of packaged water within the university campus by both staff and students, there is a need to appraise the quality status of bottled and sachet water vended and consumed in the university environment. Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta (FUNAAB) is located within peri-urban area of Abeokuta, Ogun State in southwest region of Nigeria. There is a scarcity of data regarding the quality of packaged water (sachet and pet-bottled waters) consumed in FUNAAB campus; the authors only found one published study on the quality of vended sachet water in the University site by Opafola *et al.* (2020). The findings of Opafola *et al.* (2020) indicated that while levels of tested physico-chemical properties met standards, considerable total bacteria count (TBC) existed in all analyzed sachet water samples. This present research is novel in the FUNAAB community and of public health significance to the staff and students. Therefore, this study was carried out to evaluate the impacts of prolonged storage time (1 week – 6 months) on the physico-chemical properties of sachet and pet-bottled water.

The specific objectives were (i) to appraise the effects of prolonged storage time on the concentrations of physico-chemical parameters in packaged water (ii) to compare the results of the physico-chemical levels with the drinking water guidelines of regulatory agencies (iii) to study the variations in physico-chemical characteristics of packaged water over storage time and (iv) to assess the overall quality of packaged water during storage time using the water quality index (WQI) ratings.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2. 1. Packaged Water Sample Collection, Storage and Laboratory Analysis

Two different popular brands of packaged water (sachet and pet-bottled) consumed by both students and staff of FUNAAB were selected for this study. The sampling of sachet and bottled water marques were from the packaged water companies within FUNAAB environs (Figure 1). The consumption of selected brands of packaged water is not limited to the study area, but across Abeokuta metropolis. The selection of brands was based on the preferences of students and staff, as well as university rules and regulations guiding the sale of commercially packaged water on campus. For ethical reasons, this study concealed brand names of sachet and bottled water used for the research (Ojekunle *et al.*, 2015; Sabo *et al.*, 2024). For each storage period, two samples of these packaged waters were collected from the two nearby factories within 24 hours of production (Ojekunle *et al.*, 2015; Sabo *et al.*, 2024).

Thereafter, these two samples each of sachet and bottled water were stored under room temperature conditions (25 – 30 °C) for different storage periods: a week, 2-week, 1 month, 2 months, 3 months, 4 months, 5 months and 6 months, respectively. Samples were kept in clean, dry and ventilated room in order to ensure minimal exposure to humidity, sunlight and contaminants. Bottled water remained sealed while the sachet water samples were stored by

placing them carefully on a clean plastic pallet. Each sample was labelled with code for easy identification (Figure 2) while proper recording of samples data was done for accurate tracking of their storage durations (Table 1).

Regular inspections of stored samples were also conducted throughout the storage periods. After the completion of each storage period, representative samples of sachet and bottled water were placed in chests and quickly conveyed to the laboratory for necessary preservation before commencement of physico-chemical analyses (Opafola *et al.*, 2020; Ganiyu *et al.*, 2022b).

Fig. 1. Map of the research location.

Analysis of sample was carried out in triplicates per sample per time point to determine the concentrations of selected physico-chemical properties according to American Public Health Association (APHA) (2005) specifications (Opafola *et al.*, 2020; Kusa and Joshua, 2023). The physico-chemical tests were done at SMO laboratory services, Ibadan, Nigeria.

The parameters of interest were pH, temperature, electrical conductivity (EC), total suspended solids (TSS), total dissolved solids (TDS), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), chemical oxygen demand (COD), dissolved oxygen (DO), oxidation-reduction potential (ORP), SO_4^{2-} , HCO_3^- , Cl^- , NO_3^- , K^+ , Na^+ , Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} .

The pH of packaged water samples were measured by pH meter calibrated with standard buffer solutions of pH 4, 7 and 10 after allowing the machine to equilibrate (Ganiyu *et al.*, 2022a) while temperature was measured with a Henan Wanbag EP (model MF – M51) thermometer.

Total suspended solids (TSS) was measured using the gravimetric technique by allowing a known volume of the water to pass through a pre-weighed filter paper whereby the suspended solids were deposited on the filter paper afterwards. The filter paper was dried in a desiccator and re-weighed again. Thereafter, the percentage solid deposited was calculated using weight difference gravimetrically.

Fig. 2. Sample of Sachet and Bottled waters used in this study.

Dissolved oxygen was determined by Extech instrument apparatus model DO700 which specifies concentration of DO over the range of 0.0 to 40.0 mg/l and has a resolution of 0.1/0.01 mg/l (Ganiyu *et al.*, 2022a). The major anions of SO_4^{2-} and NO_3^- were determined by ultraviolet spectrophotometric screening method and turbidimetric technique, respectively; Chloride anion was determined using silver nitrate titration method while carbonate and hydrogencarbonate ions were measured via titration process with standard acid (Ganiyu *et al.*, 2022a). For major cations, Na^+ and K^+ were determined using model 410 Corning clinical flame photometric method with air-butane gas mixture as oxidant, with calibrating standard that ranges from 5 - 100 ppm at their different filter settings. Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} concentrations were measured using the absorption mode of Model 210 VGP Buck Scientific Atomic Absorption Spectrometric (AAS) technique.

Calibration was done using standard that ranges from 1-6 ppm and 0.1-1.0 ppm, respectively at their various wavelengths. The detection limits for Na^+ and K^+ are 1.0 ppm while those for Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} are 0.5 ppm and 0.004 ppm, respectively. The ORP was determined using Jenway ORP meter. The clean electrode of the ORP meter was dipped into the water sample and allow to stabilize to take readings in the read-out phase. For BOD determination, the tested water samples were initially preserved inside a dark cupboard at normal ambient temperature (27 °C) for 5 - day period, and then their dissolved oxygen was determined utilizing the azide modification of Winkler technique (Ganiyu *et al.*, 2022b; Adesakin *et al.*, 2022). The COD was determined using the open reflux method and consequent titration with ferric ammonium sulphate (Ipeaiyeda and Obaje; 2017; Ganiyu *et al.*, 2022b). The quality control protocols employed during the analysis of physico-chemical characteristics include triplicate measurements of each parameter, calibration of scientific instruments and chemical reagents, running of blank samples for every five analyses as well as running of reference standards along with analyzed samples (Ganiyu *et al.*, 2025).

2. 2. Data Analysis

Physico-chemical data analysis was carried out using t-test with the aid of statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) software, version 20.0. The outcomes of t-test were presented as means with standard deviations and were separated at $p < 0.05$ level of significance.

2. 3. Computation of Water Quality Index

A total of ten (10) parameters were selected for the computation of water quality index. The selected parameters were pH, TDS, SO_4^{2-} , HCO_3^- , Cl^- , NO_3^- , DO, Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and K^+ . The computation of WQI for each stored packaged water was done using the formula:

$$WQI = \sum W_i q_i \quad (i)$$

where: $\sum W_i$ is the summation of relative weight, W_i is the relative weight of the *i*th parameter (Table 1) while q_i denotes the quality ranking of the specific *i*th variable (Boadi *et al.*, 2023; El Hammioui *et al.*, 2024).

W_i is computed from the relation

$$W = \frac{w_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i} \tag{ii}$$

where: w_i is the weight given to each selected variable based on its importance to the computation of the WQI while n refers to the size of considered properties in the estimation of water quality index (Boadi *et al.*, 2023; Ganiyu *et al.*, 2025).

q_i is generated from the formula

$$q_i = \left(\frac{C_i - V_i}{S_i} \right) \times 100 / 1.00 \tag{iii}$$

where: C_i is the measured concentration of a particular property i , V_i refers to the ideal concentration of the i th property (equals to zero for most physicochemical variables except DO and pH, which are 14.6 mg/l and 7.0, respectively) and S_i refers to the acceptable threshold concentration of i th property as suggested by World Health Organization standards. Specifically for DO, q_i is given by

$$q_{DO} = \left(\frac{C_i - 14.60}{S_i - 14.60} \right) \times \frac{100}{1} \tag{iv}$$

while for pH,

$$q_{pH} = \left(\frac{C_i - 7.00}{1.50} \right) \times \frac{100}{1} \tag{v}$$

The categorization of water samples based on WQI values for consumption purpose is as follows: 0 – 25 (excellent), 25 – 30 (Good), 51 – 75 (Fair), 76 – 100 (Poor) while $WQI > 100$ signifies unsuitable for drinking (Boadi *et al.*, 2023; Haider *et al.*, 2024).

Table 1. Relative weights of physico-chemical parameters used in the evaluation of WQI.

Physico- chemical parameters	Standard value S_i	Assigned weight w_i	Relative weight W_i
pH	6.5 – 8.5	4	0.129
TDS	500	4	0.129
HCO ₃ ⁻	125	3	0.097
SO ₄ ²⁻	100	4	0.129
NO ₃ ⁻	50	5	0.161

Ca ²⁺	75	2	0.065
Mg ²⁺	20	2	0.065
K ⁺	10	2	0.065
Cl ⁻	250	3	0.097
DO	5	4	0.129
		$\sum w_i = 33$	$\sum W_i = 0.999$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results of the analyzed physico-chemical parameters in sachet and bottled water samples over the storage periods are presented in Tables 2 and 3; while the result of t-test is presented in Table 4.

3. 1. Physico-chemical properties in Sachet water samples

The pH values in sachet water samples throughout the storage periods ranged from 6.68 to 7.74. All the stored sachet water samples had pH values that conformed to the acceptable limits (6.5-8.5) recommended for drinking water (WHO, 2022). The range of pH values in the sachet water samples for this study was comparable to the 6.50-7.60 range reported by Nnachetam *et al.* (2017) for samples marketed and consumed in Owerri metropolis, Imo State, Nigeria.

However, the pH range of the sachet water samples obtained in this study differs slightly from the reported pH range (6.57-6.79) in seven (7) dissimilar varieties of sachet water samples in FUNAAB by Opafola *et al.* (2020). The disparity could be as a result of difference in number of considered brands of sachet packaged water. Boadi *et al.* (2023) reported a pH range (5.38-8.03) in sachet water samples collected within Kumasi metropolis, Ghana. The difference in the pH range of sachet water samples for this study and that of Boadi *et al.* (2023) may be attributed to differences in storage periods and water sources. There is no clear trend of pH values during the storage periods.

The prolonged storage of the sachet water samples might have influenced the fluctuations of the pH values (Fadipe *et al.*, 2020). Fluctuations in pH values during the storage time may also be due to the influence of microbial activities and different physical, chemical and biochemical processes occurring within the sachet water samples; these factors may complicate attempts to predict the link between a water sample's changing chemical parameters and pH (Balogun *et al.*, 2024; Ogbonna and Ekeoma, 2025) Similar fluctuations in pH values of sachet water samples throughout the months of analyses were also reported by Fadipe *et al.* (2020) and Olanipekun *et al.* (2024). Furthermore, Saha *et al.* (2020) and Sabo *et al.* (2024) reported no clear trend of either increase or decrease in the pH values of sachet water samples over the storage durations.

The mean temperatures of the sachet water samples across the storage periods ranged from 23.92 °C (after 2-month storage) to 28.79 °C (after 5-month storage) (Table 2). Okeola *et*

al. (2023) reported a temperature range of 28.61 to 30.64 °C for sachet water samples stored under various degrees of sunlight exposure in Kwara State (North Central) Nigeria. The range of temperature values in sachet water samples throughout the storage periods for this study was within the ambient levels reported for tropical drinking water (Sabo *et al.*, 2024).

The temperatures of all the stored sachet water samples fluctuated over the storage periods. Temperature fluctuations during storage may have contributed to the inconsistent pH trends observed over the storage periods (Ahmed *et al.*, 2021). The seemingly consistent slight rise in temperature of sachet water samples after 2-5 months of storage may be linked to biochemical processes such as the growth of mesophilic microbes within the optimum temperature range of 20-45 °C (Balogun *et al.*, 2024).

The average EC values in pouched water samples varied from 0.0 to 45.0 µS/cm (after 6-month storage). All the sachet water samples had EC values below the maximum acceptable threshold (1000 µS/cm) recommended for potable water (NSDWQ, 2015; WHO, 2022). Low values of EC < 50 µS/cm indicate the efficient removal of dissolved solids by reverse osmosis water treatment system (Ogbonna and Ekeoma, 2025). The EC range (0-45 µS/cm) obtained for stored sachet water samples in this study lies within the range of 0-145 µS/cm reported for different sachet water brands within the same FUNAAB campus by Opafola *et al.* (2020). However, Ayegbo *et al.* (2021) reported a lower EC range (0.02-0.06 µS/cm) for some brands of sachet water samples sold within Sango-Ota, Ogun State, Nigeria. The EC of the sachet water samples increased slightly (though still within the permissible limit) during the first month of storage and then fluctuated until the end of the storage periods. This may be attributed to different levels of released metallic ions and ongoing microbial activities in some of the samples during storage (Adesakin *et al.*, 2024; Ogbonna and Ekeoma, 2025).

At the end of the storage periods, the TDS values in sachet water samples ranged from 0.00 to 23.29 mg/L (after 6 months of storage). TDS values of all analyzed packaged water samples throughout the entire storage periods fall within the acceptable limit of 500 mg/L for potable water (WHO, 2022). The low TDS values (< 50 mg/L) in all sachet water samples imply the use of efficient membrane filtration process during water treatment and a potential reduction in metal availability during storage (Fadipe *et al.*, 2024).

Values of TSS in sachet water samples were zero throughout the storage periods. This indicates the absence of particulate matter in all tested water samples (Opafola *et al.*, 2020). Comparable observation (0.00 - 0.01 mg/L) was also stated by Ayegbo *et al.* (2021) for sachet water samples collected from Sango- Ota, Ogun State, Nigeria. However, Opafola *et al.* (2020) reported TSS values ranging from 0.00-70.05 mg/L in seven different brands of sachet water sold and consumed within the same study area (FUNAAB).

All analyzed sachet water samples had chloride concentrations ranging from 0.00 to 37.19 mg/L which lie below the maximum acceptable standard (250 mg/L) for drinking purpose (WHO, 2022). This range differs from the 2.83-8.57 mg/L chloride range reported by Balogun *et al.* (2024) after 4 months of storage. The nitrate concentrations in sachet water samples during storage periods varied from 0 to 0.71 mg/L (after 6-month of storage) (Table 2). All the samples had nitrate levels below the maximum permissible limit (50 mg/L) set by WHO (2022) for potable water. Similar low nitrate values (less than 1 mg/L) in sachet water samples were also reported by Opafola *et al.* (2020) for the same study location. Nitrate concentrations fluctuated, rising during some months of storage and dropping in others. For example, while a decrease in nitrate level after 1 month of storage may be attributed to the presence of nitrogen-utilizing

bacteria, contrary biochemical processes likely also took place, resulting in slightly increased nitrate levels in samples at certain storage periods (Balogun *et al.*, 2024)

The values of sulphate ions in the stored sachet water samples ranged from 1.07 to 7.51 mg/L (Table 2). These sulphate levels were still lower than the maximum permissible limit of 100 mg/L specified for drinking purpose (WHO, 2022). The SO_4^{2-} range in sachet water samples over the storage periods for this study lies within the 0.95-33.71 mg/l range reported for sachet water samples by Opafola *et al.* (2020) in the same study location. There was no steady pattern in sulphate concentrations during the storage periods, as fluctuations were recorded. This variations may be partly attributed to activities of some microbes within certain sachet water samples during storage (Adesakin *et al.*, 2024; Balogun *et al.*, 2024).

Comparable fluctuations in SO_4^{2-} concentrations in sachet water samples stored for 6 weeks and 4 months were reported by Fadipe (2020) and Balogun *et al.* (2024), respectively. Low values of nitrate (0.68-1.36 mg/L) and sulphate ions (BDL-0.00 mg/L) in sachet water samples sold within University of Uyo Teaching Hospital, Akwa Ibom (South South Nigeria) were also reported by Ekanem *et al.* (2025). The carbonate and bicarbonate concentrations in sachet water samples throughout the storage periods were within the maximum allowable limits of 100 and 125 mg/L, respectively for drinking water (WHO, 2022).

The concentrations of Ca^{2+} in sachet water samples over the selected storage durations were <5.00 mg/L and far lower than the maximum permissible thresholds of 75 mg/L for consumption purpose (WHO, 2022). The Ca^{2+} range (0.00-3.35 mg/L) in the sachet water samples obtained for this study contrasts with the reported range of (2.00-161.00 mg/L for the same study location by Opafola *et al.* (2020).

Magnesium levels in sachet water samples throughout the storage periods ranged from 0.00-1.04 mg/L. Although some fluctuations were observed in some sachet water samples during the storage time, the magnesium levels in stored sachet water samples met the WHO permissible limit (20 mg/L) for drinking-purpose (WHO, 2022). Similar results of low Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} concentrations (<5 mg/L) in sachet water samples were also reported by Ugwoha and Krukru (2021) and Adesakin *et al.* (2022).

The sodium contents in the sachet water samples ranged from 1.56 to 16.76 mg/L, lying well below the maximum acceptable threshold of 200 mg/L for drinking water (WHO, 2022). Sodium ions concentrations below 5 mg/L during certain storage periods may be attributed to the efficient reverse osmosis process employed during water treatment (Fadipe *et al.*, 2024; Ogbonna and Ekeoma, 2025). There was no clear trend in Na^+ levels across the storage periods. All the stored sachet water samples had K^+ concentrations < 1.0 mg/L, and thus far below the maximum acceptable limit of 10 mg/L for drinking water (WHO, 2022).

The average concentrations of ORP in sachet water samples ranged from 80.06 mV to 135.81 mV (Table 2). All samples had ORP values less than 150 mV, suggesting weak aerobes activity (Ganiyu *et al.*, 2022b). The concentrations of dissolved oxygen (DO) in sachet water samples varied from 3.42 mg/L (after 2 months of storage) to 5.75 mg/L (after 6 months of storage). It was observed that 87% of the stored sachet water samples had DO concentrations below the permissible limit of 5 mg/L across the storage periods, while the remaining 13% had DO value that surpassed the permissible limit for drinking water.

The decrease in DO over certain storage times reflects microbial respiration and organic matter decomposition (Sabo *et al.*, 2024). Conversely, high DO concentration observed after six-month storage might be due to direct diffusion from the air through micro-gaps in the

packaging material as well as photosynthetic activity from autotrophs (Nnachetam *et al.*, 2017; Ogbonna and Ekeoma, 2025).

The BOD of sachet water samples ranged from 0.00 to 94.74 mg/L (after 1-month storage). High BOD values observed during some storage periods may be attributed to possible high microbial activities that lead to a reduction in oxygen concentration (Sabo *et al.*, 2024). The average COD concentrations in sachet water samples across the storage periods ranged from 0.00 to 85.12 mg/L. Higher COD levels during some storage periods could be attributed to a greater amount of oxidizable organic materials in the samples (Bona *et al.*, 2018).

Table 2. Concentrations of physicochemical parameters in Sachet water samples after storage times.

PARAMETERS	1 WEEK	2 WEEKS	1 MONTH	2 MONTHS	3 MONTHS	4 MONTHS	5 MONTHS	6 MONTHS
pH	6.96	7.09	6.97	7.74	6.69	7.01	6.98	7.74
TDS (mg/L)	0.00	2.88	11.61	5.02	4.94	0.00	0.00	23.29
TSS (mg/L)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
EC (μ S/cm)	0.00	5.97	23.59	10.01	9.86	0.00	0.00	45.00
COD (mg/L)	0.00	74.49	85.12	6.02	5.12	0.00	0.00	64.00
BOD (mg/L)	0.00	83.23	94.74	28.95	20.92	0.00	0.00	23.84
ORP (mV)	135.81	80.06	82.68	98.64	87.85	109.53	120.29	120.51
HCO ₃ ⁻ (mg/L)	0.00	4.84	4.34	3.26	2.39	0.00	0.00	3.68
CO ₃ ²⁻ (mg/L)	0.00	1.73	1.45	3.46	1.09	0.00	0.00	2.79
Cl ⁻ (mg/L)	0.00	20.09	19.66	24.55	19.01	0.00	0.00	37.19
SO ₄ ²⁻ (mg/L)	5.59	1.13	1.71	1.42	1.07	7.51	6.31	2.82
NO ₃ ⁻ (mg/L)	0.00	0.19	0.13	0.52	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.71
Ca ²⁺ (mg/L)	0.07	0.16	0.32	6.78	0.00	0.06	0.11	3.35
Mg ²⁺ (mg/L)	0.00	0.39	0.17	1.04	0.00	0.02	0.09	0.89
Na ⁺ (mg/L)	3.05	1.56	2.36	21.33	11.38	4.22	3.89	16.76
K ⁺ (mg/L)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.46	0.36	0.00	0.00	0.49
DO (mg/L)	3.92	4.09	4.91	3.42	3.49	4.38	4.62	5.75
Temperature(°C)	28.00	26.46	26.61	23.92	26.62	28.42	28.79	28.75

3. 2. Physico-chemical properties of Bottled water samples

The pH values in bottled water samples ranged from 6.61 to 7.98 (Table 3). The pH range in bottled water samples for this research compares well with the reported mean pH range of

6.63-7.01 in bottled water samples collected within Mekelle city (Ethiopia) by Mergia *et al.* (2025). There is a clear increase in the pH values of bottled water samples as the storage period progresses from one week to one month of storage. Nevertheless, the pH values of all stored pet-bottled water samples were within the acceptable limit (6.5 – 8.5) recommended for drinking water by WHO (2022).

The average EC values in pet-bottled water samples varied from 0.0 to 67.0 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (Table 3). The EC range in bottled water samples for this study compared well with the reported range of 8.74-31.00 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ in bottled water samples sold and consumed within Mekelle city (Ethiopia) by Mergia *et al.* (2025). All stored bottled water samples had EC concentrations below the maximum acceptable threshold (1000 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) stipulated for potable water (NSDWQ, 2015; WHO, 2022). Low values of EC < 20 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ suggests efficient removal of dissolved solids by the reverse osmosis water treatment method (Ogbonna and Ekeoma, 2025).

It was observed that the EC of bottled water samples increased slightly (though still within the acceptable limit for drinking) with storage time up to the first month, after which it fluctuated until the end of the storage. The increase in EC during the first three storage periods may be due to rising levels of dissolved materials in the samples over time (Fadipe *et al.*, 2024).

Fluctuations in EC could be partly attributed to the release of metallic ions and the physico-chemical activities occurring in some samples during the storage times (Joshua *et al.*, 2019; Ogbonna and Ekeoma, 2025).

The mean temperatures of bottled water samples ranged from 24.29 °C (2-month storage) to 29.50 °C (3-month storage) (Table 3). The occasional drop in bottled water temperature during certain storage periods could be due to some environmental factors (Balogun *et al.*, 2024). According to Epundu *et al.* (2017) and Balogun *et al.* (2024), the average water temperature must not surpass that of the location in which it is stored. The TDS values in bottled water samples ranged from 0.00 to 33.50 mg/L (after 1 month of storage). The TDS values of all stored pet-bottled water samples across the storage periods were below the acceptable limit of 500 mg/L for drinking water (WHO, 2022). The low TDS values (< 40 mg/L) in all stored bottled water samples imply an effective reverse osmosis process during water treatment and reduced metal accessibility during storage periods (Fadipe *et al.*, 2024). Values of TSS in bottled water samples were zero throughout the storage durations.

The chloride levels in bottled water samples ranged from 0.00-29.46 mg/L and fall below the maximum acceptable standard of 250 mg/L for potable water (WHO, 2022). There is a clear increase in the levels of chloride ions in bottled water samples as the storage period progresses from one week to two months. This could be associated with likely leaching from chlorine-containing compounds into the packaged water during the aforementioned periods or the possible contribution of trichloromethane from deteriorating polythene packaging materials (Adedire *et al.*, 2021; Balogun *et al.*, 2024). The nitrate concentrations in stored bottled water samples throughout the storage periods were < 0.5 mg/L and far below the maximum acceptable threshold of 50 mg/L for drinking water (WHO, 2022). However, the range of nitrate values (0.00-0.39 mg/L) in bottled water samples for this study is in contrast with the reported range of 0.11 to 2.18 mg/L in bottled water samples collected from Port-Harcourt (Nigeria) after six weeks of storage by Ugwoha and Krukru (2021).

The average sulphate concentrations in stored bottled water samples ranged from 0.00 to 5.86 mg/L (Table 3). All bottled water samples, irrespective of storage durations, had sulphate contents that conformed to the acceptable limit of 100 mg/L recommended for potable water (WHO, 2022).

As observed in sachet water samples, there was no steady pattern in sulphate levels during the storage periods, as some inconsistent figures were recorded. Nevertheless, the SO_4^{2-} range in stored bottled water samples being lower than that of sachet water for the present study concurs with alike observation by Okeola *et al.* (2023). The carbonate and bicarbonate concentrations in the bottled water samples for each of the investigated storage periods were within the maximum allowable limits of 100 mg/L and 125 mg/L, respectively for drinking water (WHO, 2022).

The concentrations of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} in bottled water samples over the selected storage periods were <5.00 mg/L and 1.00 mg/L, respectively. The levels of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} in stored bottled water samples were far lower than their permissible maximum thresholds of 75 mg/L and 20 mg/L, respectively for consumption purpose (WHO, 2022). The results for Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} concentrations in stored bottled water samples indicate an over-demineralization effect from the reverse osmotic process utilized for treated water (Dougna *et al.*, 2024). The average concentrations of ORP in bottled water samples ranged from 69.41 mV (after 1 month of storage) to 132.02 mV (after 4 months of storage) (Table 3).

Dissolved oxygen (DO) in bottled water samples varied from 2.89 mg/L to 6.29 mg/L. There were fluctuations, with DO values rising during some months of storage while dropping in others. The reduction in DO values over some storage periods indicates potential bacteria respiration of organic materials in some samples (Duru *et al.*, 2017; Sabo *et al.*, 2024). The maximum DO concentration was recorded after six-month storage and could be due to oxygen permeation through the micro-gaps of the plastic packaging materials from the surrounding atmosphere (Nnachetam *et al.*, 2017; Ogbonna and Ekeoma, 2025).

The concentrations of BOD and COD in pet-bottled water samples ranged from 0.00 to 72.28 mg/L (after 1-month storage) and 0.00 to 56.11 mg/L (after 1 month storage), respectively (Table 3). Close observation of the trends in BOD and COD values throughout the storage durations revealed that the maximum values of BOD and COD were recorded in the one-month storage samples. Specifically, bottled water samples stored for more than one week (2 weeks, 1, 2, 3 and 6 months) had BOD and COD concentrations that surpassed the acceptable thresholds of 5 and 10 mg/L, correspondingly for drinking water (WHO, 2022). The BOD and COD values exceeding drinking water limits in many storage periods could be attributed to microbial regrowth and the possible presence of oxidizable organic materials in the samples (Binibor *et al.*, 2025; Ogbonna and Ekeoma, 2025). The BOD and COD values were zero in the 4- and 5- month storage bottled water samples. The mechanism for this occurrence could be due to microbial inactivity or low population, depletion of biodegradable organic matter, and analytical sensitivity detection limits during the concerned months of storage (Aguilar-Torrejón *et al.*, 2023; Lacalamita *et al.*, 2024; Zha *et al.*, 2025).

Table 3. Concentrations of physicochemical parameters in Bottled water samples after storage times.

PARAMETERS	1 WEEK	2 WEEKS	1 MONTH	2 MONTHS	3 MONTHS	4 MONTHS	5 MONTHS	6 MONTHS
pH	6.61	7.03	7.43	7.98	6.82	6.67	6.69	7.46
TDS (mg/L)	5.00	8.73	33.50	2.01	1.95	0.00	4.00	0.50

TSS (mg/L)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
EC ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	10.00	17.16	67.00	4.03	3.81	0.00	8.00	1.00
COD (mg/L)	0.00	47.80	56.11	11.15	9.96	0.00	0.00	0.00
BOD (mg/L)	0.00	57.60	72.28	32.44	24.77	0.00	0.00	0.00
ORP (mV)	127.55	75.57	69.41	87.21	71.18	132.20	109.42	109.34
HCO_3^- (mg/L)	0.00	2.94	2.59	4.34	2.56	0.00	0.00	0.00
CO_3^{2-} (mg/L)	0.00	1.57	1.19	3.09	1.12	0.00	0.00	0.00
Cl^- (mg/L)	0.00	15.37	16.05	29.46	21.39	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO_4^{2-} (mg/L)	5.11	0.00	0.00	1.90	0.91	5.47	5.86	5.50
NO_3^- (mg/L)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.39	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Ca^{2+} (mg/L)	0.00	0.00	0.00	4.16	0.00	0.04	0.45	0.17
Mg^{2+} (mg/L)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.74	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00
Na^+ (mg/L)	2.29	4.21	13.20	17.55	9.98	2.22	0.00	0.00
K^+ (mg/L)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.54	0.52	0.00	0.00	0.00
DO (mg/L)	4.49	3.65	3.67	5.10	2.89	5.72	4.74	6.29
Temperature($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	27.92	26.64	27.13	24.29	29.50	28.21	28.23	28.08

3. 3. Physico-chemical properties of Sachet and Bottled water samples

The pH values of sachet and bottled water samples varied from 6.68 to 7.74 and 6.61 to 7.98, respectively. It was observed that maximum values of pH in sachet and bottled water samples were recorded after 6-month storage (Tables 2 and 3). The pH values obtained for packaged water samples in this study are significantly different across the storage periods ($p < 0.05$).

The mean temperatures of sachet and bottled water samples ranged from 23.92 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 28.79 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 24.29 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 29.50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively (Tables 2 and 3). Occasional drops in water temperatures observed during certain storage periods for both sachet and bottled water samples may be attributed to different environmental factors (Danso-Boateng *et al.*, 2013; Balogun *et al.*, 2024). The temperature values recorded for both stored sachet and bottled water samples fall within the ambient temperature of the storage location. The mean water temperature values of investigated packaged water samples are significantly different across the storage periods at $p < 0.05$ level (Table 4).

The average EC values in pouched and pet-bottled water samples varied from 0.0 to 45.0 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and 0.0 to 67.0 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, respectively. All the packaged water samples had EC concentrations below the maximum acceptable threshold of 1000 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ recommended for potable water (WHO, 2022). The ranges of EC values in both sachet and bottled water samples were quite below the reported range of 45.33-160.12 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ in packaged water samples by Okeola *et al.* (2023). There was no significant difference in the mean EC values of both sachet

and bottled water samples among the storage time at $p < 0.05$ level (Table 4). The range of TDS concentrations in sachet and bottled water samples varied from 0.00 to 23.29 mg/L and 0.00 to 33.50 mg/L, correspondingly. Comparatively, the ranges of TDS values in sachet and bottled water samples in this research differ from the reported TDS range (22.03-81.00 mg/L) for stored packaged water under sunlight exposure after six weeks by Okeola *et al.* (2023). The TSS was not detected in any sachet or bottled water samples across all storage durations. There were no significant differences in the mean values of TDS and TSS between sachet and bottled water samples throughout the storage periods at $p < 0.05$ level (Table 4).

The nitrate concentrations in sachet and bottled water samples varied from 0.00 to 0.71 mg/L and 0.00 to 0.39 mg/L, respectively. However, the ranges of nitrate concentrations in investigated packaged water samples for this study were lower than the range (2.11-8.47 mg/L) reported by Okeola *et al.* (2023) for sachet and bottled water stored under diverse sunlight conditions. It should be noted that very low concentrations of nitrate ions in the packaged water samples over the storage durations could be an indication of low microbial proliferation in analyzed water samples, even when the ecological conditions are favourable (Adesakin *et al.*, 2022). There was no significant difference in mean nitrate values for both sachet and bottled water over the storage periods as shown in Table 4.

The average sulphate concentrations in stored sachet and bottled water samples ranged from 1.07 to 7.51 mg/L and 0.00 to 5.86 mg/L, respectively. The range of SO_4^{2-} concentration in the sachet and bottled water samples throughout the storage periods was comparatively high than the range (0.01-0.15 mg/L) reported by Okeola *et al.* (2023) for both water types. The carbonate and bicarbonate concentrations in sachet and bottled water samples for each of the storage periods were within the maximum allowable limits of 100 and 125 mg/L, respectively for drinking water (WHO, 2022). There are significant differences in the mean values of bicarbonate and carbonate ions in stored packaged water samples across the storage durations at $p < 0.05$ (Table 4).

The concentrations of divalent ions (Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+}) in sachet and bottled water samples over the selected storage durations were < 5.00 mg/L. Similar results of low Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} concentrations (< 5 mg/L) in packaged water samples were also reported by Ugwoha and Krukru (2021), Adesakin *et al.* (2022) and Okpara *et al.* (2024). Low levels of TDS, EC, Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} in the stored packaged water samples throughout the storage periods indicate over – demineralization during the reverse osmosis process of water treatment (Dougna *et al.*, 2024). While these findings advocate slight chemical pollution, lack of needed minerals may compromise the nutritive quality of the treated water, demanding improvement in water treatment practices (Mani *et al.*, 2023; Dougna *et al.*, 2024).

The average concentrations of ORP in sachet and bottled water samples ranged from 80.06 mV to 135.81 mV and 69.41 mV to 132.02 mV, respectively (Tables 2 and 3). All the samples had ORP values less than 150 mV, indicating possible weak aerobes activities. There was significant difference in mean ORP concentrations for both water types among the storage durations at $p < 0.05$ level (Table 4).

The dissolved oxygen concentrations in sachet and bottled water samples varied from 3.42 to 5.75 mg/L and 2.89- 6.29 mg/L, respectively. Specifically, maximum DO values were recorded in samples stored for six months (sachet and bottled water). The t-test results revealed no significant difference in mean DO values between the sachet and bottled, nor across the different storage durations ($p < 0.05$) (Table 4). The BOD concentrations in sachet and bottled water ranged from 0.00 to 94.74 mg/L and 0.00 to 72.28 mg/L, respectively. The average COD

concentrations in sachet and bottled water samples throughout the storage periods ranged from 0 to 85.12 mg/L and 0 to 56.11 mg/L, respectively. Close observations of both BOD and COD trends throughout the storage durations revealed that the highest values of both parameters in sachet and bottled water samples were recorded after one month of storage. Furthermore, BOD and COD levels in both sachet and bottled water samples surpassed permissible drinking water limits at multiple storage periods. The mean BOD and COD values in both water types are statistically significantly different across the storage durations at the $p < 0.05$ level (Table 4).

Generally, fluctuations in the values of some physico-chemical properties of packaged water samples over the storage durations, as observed in this study, are consistent with similar observations by Saha *et al.* (2020), Sabo *et al.* (2024) and Balogun *et al.* (2024). These variations in the trends of some parameters with storage periods perhaps indicate potential differences in water sources, adopted treatment processes and water quality over the storage periods (Sabo *et al.*, 2024).

It was apparent from this research that studied brands of sachet and bottled water samples after 7-day of production met the acceptable guideline standards for tested physico-chemical parameters in drinking water (NSDWQ, 2015; WHO, 2022).

Table 4. Results of t-test for physico-chemical parameters in Sachet and Bottled water samples.

Parameters	Container	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
pH	Sachet Water	8	6.69	7.74	7.15	0.39
	Bottled water	8	6.61	7.98	7.09	0.49
TDS	Sachet Water	8	0.00	23.29	5.97	8.02
	Bottled water	8	0.00	33.50	6.96	11.08
TSS	Sachet Water	8	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Bottled water	8	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
EC	Sachet Water	8	0.00	45.00	11.80	15.58
	Bottled water	8	0.00	67.00	13.87	22.17
COD	Sachet Water	8	0.00	85.12	29.34	37.92
	Bottled water	8	0.00	56.11	15.63	23.00
BOD	Sachet Water	8	0.00	94.74	31.46	37.47
	Bottled water	8	0.00	72.28	23.39	28.87
ORP	Sachet Water	8	80.06	135.81	104.42	20.34
	Bottled water	8	69.41	132.20	97.73	25.24
HCO ₃ ⁻	Sachet Water	8	0.00	4.84	2.31	2.05
	Bottled water	8	0.00	4.34	1.55	1.75

CO ₃ ²⁻	Sachet Water	8	0.00	3.46	1.32	1.32
	Bottled water	8	0.00	3.09	0.87	1.11
Cl ⁻	Sachet Water	8	0.00	37.19	15.06	13.74
	Bottled water	8	0.00	29.46	10.28	11.79
SO ₄ ²⁻	Sachet Water	8	1.07	7.51	3.44	2.61
	Bottled water	8	0.00	5.86	3.09	2.63
NO ₃ ⁻	Sachet Water	8	0.00	0.71	0.19	0.27
	Bottled water	8	0.00	0.39	0.05	0.14
Ca ²⁺	Sachet Water	8	0.00	6.78	1.36	2.47
	Bottled water	8	0.00	4.16	0.60	1.45
Mg ²⁺	Sachet Water	8	0.00	1.04	0.33	0.42
	Bottled water	8	0.00	0.74	0.10	0.26
Na ⁺	Sachet Water	8	1.56	21.33	8.07	7.51
	Bottled water	8	0.00	17.55	6.18	6.59
K ⁺	Sachet Water	8	0.00	0.50	0.16	0.23
	Bottled water	8	0.00	0.54	0.13	0.24
DO	Sachet Water	8	3.42	5.75	4.32	0.78
	Bottled water	8	2.89	6.29	4.57	1.14
Temperature	Sachet Water	8	23.92	28.79	27.19	1.65
	Bottled water	8	24.29	29.50	27.50	1.55

Similar superscripts along the column are not significantly different ($p < 0.05$)

3. 4. Water Quality Index Values of packaged water samples

The WQI values for sachet and bottled water throughout the storage periods ranged from 14 to 19 and 12 to 18, respectively (Tables 5 and 6). An analysis of the sub-index (q_iW_i) components of the WQI revealed that dissolved oxygen constituted on average 87.85% and 90.46% of the total WQI values of sachet and bottled water, respectively. The individual WQI values of the packaged water (sachet and bottled water) remained below 20 throughout the storage period, indicating excellent quality (Tables 5 and 6).

This provides a further indication that the analyzed packaged water samples had acceptable levels for most of the tested physico-chemical properties over the storage period, thereby reflecting their suitability for drinking. However, the elevated BOD and COD levels observed during several storage periods are concerning and require further attention.

Table 5. Water Quality Index for Sachet Water samples for each storage period.

$q_i W_i$	1 WEEK	2 WEEK	1 MONTH	2 MONTHS	3 MONTHS	4 MONTHS	5 MONTHS	6 MONTHS
DO	14.36	14.13	13.02	15.02	14.93	13.73	13.41	11.89
TDS	0.00	0.07	0.23	0.13	0.13	0.00	0.00	0.60
HCO ₃ ⁻	0.00	0.37	0.34	0.25	0.19	0.00	0.00	0.28
SO ₄ ²⁻	0.72	0.15	0.22	0.18	0.14	0.99	0.81	0.36
NO ₃ ⁻	0.00	0.06	0.04	0.17	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.23
Ca ²⁺	0.00	0.01	0.03	0.53	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.29
Mg ²⁺	0.00	0.12	0.05	0.34	0.00	0.01	0.03	0.29
Na ⁺	0.09	0.05	0.07	0.69	0.37	0.14	0.13	0.54
K ⁺	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.29	0.23	0.00	0.00	0.32
Cl ⁻	0.00	0.78	0.76	0.95	0.74	0.00	0.00	1.44
WQI	15.00	16.00	15.00	19.00	17.00	15.00	14.00	16.00

Table 6. Water Quality Index for Bottled Water samples for each storage period.

$q_i W_i$	1 WEEK	2 WEEK	1 MONTH	2 MONTHS	3 MONTHS	4 MONTHS	5 MONTHS	6 MONTHS
DO	13.59	14.71	14.69	12.77	15.74	11.93	13.25	11.17
TDS	0.13	0.26	0.86	0.05	0.05	0.00	0.10	0.01
HCO ₃ ⁻	0.00	0.23	0.20	0.34	0.19	0.00	0.00	0.00
SO ₄ ²⁻	0.65	0.00	0.00	0.25	0.12	0.70	0.76	0.71
NO ₃ ⁻	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.13	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Ca ²⁺	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.36	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.01
Mg ²⁺	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.24	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00
Na ⁺	0.07	0.14	0.43	0.57	0.32	0.07	0.00	0.00
K ⁺	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.35	0.34	0.00	0.00	0.00
Cl ⁻	0.00	0.59	0.62	1.14	0.83	0.00	0.00	0.00
WQI	14.00	16.00	17.00	16.00	18.00	13.00	14.00	12.00

The excellent quality of packaged water samples observed in this study concurs with similar findings by Umar *et al.* (2020), who reported a WQI range of 4.96 - 21.95 for different bottled water brands consumed in Minna, North Central Nigeria. Furthermore, a study by Taiwo *et al.* (2023) found that sachet water consumed in Abeokuta and Sagamu, in Southwest, Nigeria exhibited good to excellent quality according to WQI ratings. Yilkal *et al.* (2019) also reported that WQI values of bottled water marketed in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia ranged from 3.85 to 49.20, indicating an excellent to good quality status.

Additionally, similar favourable packaged water quality was also reported by Ugwoha and Krukru (2021) who reported WQI values between 1.24 and 38.88 and Boadi *et al.* (2023), who observed an average WQI of 6.21 for sachet water samples in Kumasi, Ghana.

The excellent quality of bottled water after a 6-month storage period aligns with the assertion by Zha *et al.* (2025) that mineral water remains potable for at least 12 months. It should be noted that the WQI ranges for sachet and bottled water obtained in this study contrast with the range of 55-71 reported for groundwater samples from wells in Khenifra Province, Morocco by El Hammioui *et al.* (2024, 2025).

3. 5. Limitations of the Study

It should be noted that the research focuses exclusively on the physicochemical characteristics of packaged water samples stored over a prolonged period. Future research should incorporate potentially toxic elements and microbial analyses to fully assess the impact of prolonged storage on the quality of sachet and bottled water.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The present study investigates the impact of extended storage time on the levels of physico-chemical parameters of two popular brands of sachet and pet-bottled consumed on the FUNAAB campus. The findings reveal that concentrations of some physico-chemical parameters remain within the allowable limits specified by global and Nigerian regulatory standards for potable water across the storage durations.

The outcomes obtained revealed that most of the physico-chemical variables were within the allowable limits set by the World Health Organization and Standard Organization of Nigeria for drinking water throughout the storage durations. All stored sachet and pet-bottled samples exhibited “excellent” status and thus fit for drinking based on water quality index categorization. However, after six months of storage, sachet and bottled samples exhibited maximum DO values that exceeded the allowable limit for safe drinking water.

Furthermore, distinctly higher values of BOD and COD (exceeding acceptable limits) in the analyzed samples were recorded from two weeks up to three months of storage; these findings thus warrant careful consideration. Relevant regulatory agencies should ensure that packaged water factories unceasingly complied with standard water treatment processes for improved public health in the study location.

These findings highlight the need for improved hygienic practices within packaged water facilities, adequate water treatment processes, and stricter quality control measures by relevant regulatory agencies. Further research are recommended to assess the levels of bacteriological indicators and potentially toxic elements in packaged water samples over prolonged storage periods.

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